

Appendix S1. Additional data visualizations, model selections and summaries

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Support that *Galerucella* drive increased herbivory of *L. salicaria* (Fig. S1):

Figure S1. Estimated marginal means and 95% confidence intervals for mixed effects regression (binomial distribution) evaluating whether presence of *Galerucella* eggs predict *L. salicaria* herbivory. Our model predicts we are significantly more likely ($P < 0.001$) to detect herbivory on *L. salicaria* when *Galerucella* eggs are found within the quadrat. In our regression, we included fixed effects of presence/absence of *Galerucella* eggs as well as *L. salicaria* stem density (log transformed). We also included random intercepts for calendar year and quadrat nested within site nested within region.

Table S1. List of 33 long-term monitoring sites across four regions in New York State. Sites ordered from west to east. G, H, and N superscripts indicate releases included *Galerucella*, *H. transversovittatus*, or *N. marmoratus*, respectively. Year of confirmed establishment is the first spring we detected *Galerucella* at a site following releases the previous year (*i.e.*, *Galerucella* successfully overwintered and/or produced subsequent generations).

Region	Site	Latitude	Longitude	# of quadrats	Year of releases	Confirmed establishment of <i>Galerucella</i>
					1992 ^{GHN}	
Western New York	Paddy5	43.11184	-78.48950	7		1996
Western New York	Braddock	43.29990	-77.72023	5	1995 ^G	1996
Montezuma	Eagle	43.02026	-76.80413	15	1999 ^G , 2000 ^G , 2001 ^G	2000
Montezuma	Wood	42.99181	-76.79056	15	1999 ^G , 2000 ^{GH} , 2001 ^{GH}	2000
Montezuma	Tschache	42.98952	-76.77153	15	1999 ^G , 2000 ^{GH} , 2001 ^{GH}	2000
Montezuma	Nature Center	43.08996	-76.76271	10	1999 ^G , 2000 ^G , 2001 ^G	2000
Montezuma	Kazinski	43.04579	-76.75250	15	<i>no releases</i>	2003
Montezuma	Malone	43.07422	-76.74643	15	1999 ^G , 2000 ^G , 2001 ^G	2000
Montezuma	Railroad	43.05694	-76.71910	15	1999 ^G , 2000 ^{GH} , 2001 ^{GH}	2000
Montezuma	Martens	43.09002	-76.70546	15	1999 ^G , 2000 ^G , 2001 ^G	2000
Montezuma	Curran	43.12948	-76.69994	15	2000 ^H , 2001 ^H	2000
Montezuma	Hwy31	43.01719	-76.69955	15	2000 ^H , 2001 ^H	2001
Montezuma	Frost	43.10707	-76.69105	15	1999 ^G , 2000 ^{GH} , 2001 ^{GH}	2000
Montezuma	Loop	43.04563	-76.68998	8	1999 ^G , 2000 ^G , 2001 ^G	2000
Montezuma	Pintail	43.08131	-76.67686	15	2000 ^H , 2001 ^H	2001
Montezuma	Cook	43.09369	-76.67476	15	<i>no releases</i>	2001
Montezuma	Goose	43.08450	-76.67092	15	1999 ^G , 2000 ^G , 2001 ^G	2000
Montezuma	Maiden	43.04829	-76.66963	15	2000 ^H , 2001 ^H	2000
Montezuma	Spring Lake	43.10068	-76.65606	15	<i>no releases</i>	2002
Montezuma	Hwy38	43.09644	-76.64698	15	2000 ^H , 2001 ^H	2002
Montezuma	Misty	43.05613	-76.62087	15	<i>no releases</i>	2003
Eastern Lake Ontario	El Dorado	43.80685	-76.23448	5	2006 ^G	2007
Eastern Lake Ontario	Dixon	43.78785	-76.22221	3	2006 ^G	—
Eastern Lake Ontario	Harriman	43.78460	-76.22078	2	2006 ^G	2007
Eastern Lake Ontario	Southwick	43.76076	-76.21319	5	2006 ^G	2007
Eastern Lake Ontario	Lakeview	43.74627	-76.20248	5	2006 ^G	2007
Eastern Lake Ontario	North Colwell	43.71332	-76.19806	1	2006 ^G	2007
Eastern Lake Ontario	Rainbow	43.61697	-76.19704	1	2006 ^G	2007
Eastern Lake Ontario	South Colwell	43.69723	-76.19108	5	2006 ^G	2007
Hudson River Valley	Gale	41.64308	-74.21009	10	1995 ^H , 1997 ^G	—
Hudson River Valley	Stewart	41.50044	-74.13570	6	1996 ^G , 1997 ^H	1999
Hudson River Valley	Stony	41.54072	-73.94954	6	1995 ^H , 1996 ^G	1999
Hudson River Valley	Athens	42.25584	-73.82406	6	1998 ^G	1999

Model selection process for evaluating biological success

Below, we report all candidate models fit to evaluate biological success (Tables S2–S8). For all models, we included calendar year and quadrat nested within site as random intercepts. For each response variable, we fit all candidate generalized additive mixed models (GAMMs) in two ways: with a single spline for time or with separate splines for time for each sampling region. We then used the R function `aictab` in the `AICcmodavg` package (Mazerolle, 2020) to identify the ‘best’ model as the model with the lowest AICc value, a conservative version of Akaike information criterion (following Burnham and Anderson, 2002). For Tables S2–S8, k refers to the maximum allowed number of turning points in the spline, with $k=1$ representing a linear relationship. ΔAICc is calculated as the lowest model AICc value subtracted from the AICc of the given model. Akaike weight (w_i) is the relative likelihood that the model is explaining the data better than the remaining models in the set (*i.e.*, the model likelihood normalized by the sum of all model likelihoods). After our initial model comparison, we removed models with uninformative parameters (Arnold 2010; Leroux 2019) and recalculated Akaike weights ($\text{adj. } w_i$) on this reduced set of competing models. Note: for each analysis, the best model was rerun using Restricted Maximum Likelihood Estimation (REML=TRUE). We depict select predictions of the best models in Figs S2 & S3.

Biological success: model selection summaries (Tables S2–S8) and associated visualizations (Figs. S2 & S3)

Table S2. Candidate GAMMs (binomial distributions) for evaluating change in the probability that quadrats are occupied by *L. salicaria* over time. In our full model, we included fixed effects of latitude and longitude in addition to the spline(s) for time. Note: the full model with separate splines for each region led to complete separation of the data and was not included in model comparisons.

Model	k	-log-lik	AICc	ΔAICc	w_i	$\text{adj. } w_i$
single spline + latitude	7	-179.62	373.32	0.00	0.54	0.68
single spline + longitude + latitude	8	-179.60	375.32	2.00	0.20	
splines by region + latitude	13	-174.84	375.95	2.64	0.14	0.18
single spline + longitude	7	-181.49	377.07	3.75	0.08	0.10
single spline	6	-183.81	379.68	6.37	0.02	0.03
splines by region	12	-178.85	381.94	8.62	0.01	0.01
splines by region + longitude	13	-178.04	382.36	9.04	0.01	

Table S3. Candidate GAMMs (negative binomial distributions) for evaluating change in *L. salicaria* stem density over time for quadrats occupied by *L. salicaria*. In our full model, we included fixed effects of latitude, longitude, and initial *L. salicaria* stem density at the start of monitoring (log-transformed) in addition to the spline(s) for time.

	Model	k	-log-lik	AICc	Δ AICc	w _i	adj.w _i
	single spline + initial stem density + longitude	9	-4396.14	8810.44	0.00	0.51	0.67
	single spline + initial stem density + latitude	9	-4396.90	8811.95	1.51	0.24	0.32
	single spline + initial stem density + longitude + latitude	10	-4395.91	8812.00	1.56	0.24	
	splines by region + initial stem density + longitude	15	-4394.66	8819.73	9.29	0.00	0.01
	splines by region + initial stem density + latitude	15	-4395.35	8821.11	10.67	0.00	0.00
	splines by region + initial stem density + longitude + latitude	16	-4394.62	8821.70	11.26	0.00	
	single spline + initial stem density	8	-4403.47	8823.06	12.62	0.00	0.00
	splines by region + initial stem density	14	-4397.60	8823.55	13.11	0.00	0.00
	single spline	7	-4465.90	8945.90	135.46	0.00	0.00
	splines by region	13	-4461.20	8948.71	138.27	0.00	0.00

Figure S2. Model predictions from the best GAMM (negative binomial distribution) evaluating how *L. salicaria* stem density changed over time. Lines represent 0th, 25th, 50th, 75th, and 100th quantiles (lowest to highest lines, respectively) of initial *L. salicaria* density at the start of monitoring. We included a single spline for time across all regions, fixed effects of initial stem density (log transformed) and longitude, and random intercepts for calendar year and quadrat nested within site. The density of *L. salicaria* stems is predicted to decrease over time, but quadrats are still expected to have higher densities of *L. salicaria* stems 25+ years following insect release if they had higher densities of *L. salicaria* stems at the start of monitoring.

Table S4. Candidate GAMMs (Gaussian) for evaluating change in height of the five tallest *L. salicaria* stems per quadrat over time. In our full model, we included fixed effects of initial stem density (log transformed), latitude, and longitude. These models were not interpreted in the manuscript because they were a poor fit—factors other than time, stem density, and location likely influence changes in stem height.

	Model	k	-log-lik	AICc	Δ AICc	w_i	adj. w_i
smoothers by area + initial stem density		14	-26517.09	53062.26	0.00	0.33	0.96
smoothers by area + initial stem density + latitude		15	-26516.16	53062.41	0.15	0.31	
smoothers by area + initial stem density + longitude		15	-26516.44	53062.97	0.70	0.23	
smoothers by area + initial stem density + longitude + latitude		16	-26516.15	53064.40	2.14	0.11	
smoothers by area		13	-26521.31	53068.68	6.41	0.01	0.04
single smoother + initial stem density		8	-26661.08	53338.19	275.93	0.00	0.00
single smoother + initial stem density + longitude		9	-26660.94	53339.90	277.64	0.00	
single smoother + initial stem density + latitude		9	-26661.07	53340.18	277.92	0.00	
single smoother + initial stem density + longitude + latitude		10	-26660.87	53341.79	279.52	0.00	
single smoother		7	-26666.07	53346.15	283.89	0.00	0.00

Table S5. Candidate GAMMs (binomial distributions) for evaluating change in the proportion of the five tallest *L. salicaria* stems per quadrat that were fertile over time. In our full model, we included fixed effects of initial stem density (log transformed), stem height, latitude, and longitude.

	Model	k	-log-lik	AICc	ΔAICc	w_i	adj. w_i
	smoothers by area + initial stem density + stem height + longitude	15	-1145.78	2321.65	0.00	0.39	0.55
	smoothers by area + initial stem density + stem height + latitude	15	-1146.04	2322.16	0.51	0.30	0.42
	smoothers by area + initial stem density + stem height + longitude + latitude	16	-1145.16	2322.41	0.76	0.27	
	smoothers by area + stem height	13	-1150.86	2327.79	6.15	0.02	0.03
	smoothers by area + initial stem density + stem height	14	-1149.96	2328.00	6.36	0.02	
	single smoother + initial stem density + stem height + latitude	9	-1159.73	2337.49	15.85	0.00	0.00
	single smoother + initial stem density + stem height + longitude + latitude	10	-1159.25	2338.54	16.89	0.00	
	single smoother + initial stem density + stem height + longitude	9	-1160.44	2338.92	17.27	0.00	0.00
	single smoother + stem height	7	-1165.09	2344.19	22.55	0.00	0.00
	single smoother + initial stem density + stem height	8	-1165.07	2346.17	24.52	0.00	
	smoothers by area + initial stem density	13	-1647.33	3320.73	999.08	0.00	0.00
	single smoother + initial stem density	7	-1681.08	3376.18	1054.53	0.00	0.00
	single smoother	6	-1682.63	3377.27	1055.63	0.00	0.00
	smoothers by area	12	-1691.98	3408.02	1086.38	0.00	0.00

Table S6. Candidate GAMMs (Gaussian distributions) for evaluating how number of inflorescences (log-transformed) changed over time for the subset of five tallest *L. salicaria* stems per quadrat that were fertile. In our full model, we included fixed effects of initial stem density (log transformed), stem height, latitude, and longitude.

	Model	k	-log-lik	AICc	Δ AICc	w_i	adj. w_i
smoothers by area + stem height + initial stem density	15	-4205.33	8440.78	0.00	0.32	0.50	
smoothers by area + stem height + initial stem density + longitude + latitude	17	-4203.33	8440.80	0.02	0.32	0.50	
smoothers by area + stem height + initial stem density + longitude	16	-4204.66	8441.44	0.66	0.23		
smoothers by area + stem height + initial stem density + latitude	16	-4205.31	8442.75	1.97	0.12		
smoothers by area + stem height	14	-4212.58	8453.26	12.49	0.00	0.00	
smoothers by area + stem height + longitude	15	-4212.15	8454.40	13.63	0.00		
smoothers by area + stem height + longitude + latitude	16	-4211.61	8455.35	14.58	0.00		
smoothers by area + stem height + latitude	15	-4212.88	8455.87	15.09	0.00	0.00	
single smoother + stem height + initial stem density	9	-4227.07	8472.18	31.41	0.00	0.00	
single smoother + stem height + initial stem density + latitude	10	-4226.58	8473.22	32.44	0.00		
single smoother + stem height + initial stem density + longitude	10	-4226.82	8473.69	32.92	0.00		
single smoother + stem height + initial stem density + longitude + latitude	11	-4226.57	8475.21	34.43	0.00		
single smoother + stem height	8	-4234.70	8485.43	44.65	0.00	0.00	
single smoother + stem height + latitude	9	-4234.11	8486.26	45.49	0.00		
single smoother + stem height + longitude	9	-4234.50	8487.04	46.27	0.00		
single smoother + stem height + longitude + latitude	10	-4234.05	8488.16	47.38	0.00		
smoothers by area	13	-4557.92	9141.93	701.15	0.00	0.00	
single smoother	7	-4590.90	9195.83	755.05	0.00	0.00	

Table S7. Candidate GAMMs (Gaussian distributions) for evaluating how inflorescence length (square root transformed) changed over time for the subset of five tallest *L. salicaria* stems per quadrat that were fertile. In our full model, we included fixed effects of initial stem density (log transformed), stem height, latitude, and longitude.

	Model	k	-log-lik	AICc	Δ AICc	w_i	adj. w_i
	smoothers by area + stem height + initial stem density + latitude	16	-6487.51	13007.14	0.00	0.41	0.62
	smoothers by area + stem height + initial stem density + longitude + latitude	17	-6486.82	13007.77	0.64	0.30	
	smoothers by area + stem height + initial stem density + longitude	16	-6488.36	13008.85	1.71	0.17	0.26
	smoothers by area + stem height + latitude	15	-6491.04	13012.18	5.04	0.03	0.05
	smoothers by area + stem height + longitude + latitude	16	-6490.27	13012.66	5.52	0.03	
	smoothers by area + stem height + longitude	15	-6491.40	13012.92	5.78	0.02	0.03
	single smoother + stem height + initial stem density + longitude	10	-6496.92	13013.89	6.75	0.01	0.02
	single smoother + stem height + initial stem density + longitude + latitude	11	-6496.47	13015.00	7.86	0.01	
	single smoother + stem height + initial stem density + latitude	10	-6498.30	13016.65	9.51	0.00	0.01
	single smoother + stem height + longitude	9	-6499.31	13016.67	9.53	0.00	0.01
	single smoother + stem height + latitude	9	-6499.51	13017.06	9.92	0.00	0.00
	single smoother + stem height + longitude + latitude	10	-6499.00	13018.04	10.91	0.00	
	single smoother + stem height + initial stem density	9	-6501.02	13020.09	12.95	0.00	0.00
	smoothers by area + stem height + initial stem density	15	-6496.60	13023.30	16.17	0.00	0.00
	single smoother + stem height	8	-6503.76	13023.55	16.41	0.00	0.00
	smoothers by area + stem height	14	-6499.35	13026.80	19.67	0.00	0.00
	smoothers by area	13	-6961.28	13948.65	941.51	0.00	0.00
	single smoother	7	-6980.82	13975.67	968.54	0.00	0.00

Table S8. Candidate GAMMs (Gaussian distributions) for evaluating change in flower density (square root transformed) over time for the subset of five tallest *L. salicaria* stems per quadrat that were fertile. In our full model, we included fixed effects of initial stem density (log transformed), inflorescence length (square root transformed), stem height, latitude, and longitude.

	Model	k	-log-lik	AICc	Δ AICc	w _i	adj. w _i
	smoothers by area + inflorescence length + stem height + longitude + latitude	17	-7360.00	14754.13	0.00	0.39	0.59
	smoothers by area + inflorescence length + stem height + longitude	16	-7361.54	14755.20	1.07	0.23	0.35
	smoothers by area + inflorescence length + stem height + initial stem density + longitude + latitude	18	-7359.66	14755.48	1.35	0.20	
	smoother by area + inflorescence length + stem height + initial stem density + longitude	17	-7361.32	14756.78	2.65	0.10	
	smoothers by area + inflorescence length + stem height	15	-7364.31	14758.73	4.60	0.04	0.06
	smoothers by area + inflorescence length + stem height + latitude	16	-7364.04	14760.20	6.07	0.02	
	smoothers by area + inflorescence length + stem height + initial stem density	16	-7364.09	14760.30	6.17	0.02	
	smoothers by area + inflorescence length + stem height + initial stem density + latitude	17	-7363.84	14761.82	7.69	0.01	
	smoothers by area + inflorescence length + longitude + latitude	16	-7381.98	14796.08	41.95	0.00	0.00
	smoothers by area + inflorescence length + longitude	15	-7383.61	14797.32	43.19	0.00	0.00
	smoothers by area + inflorescence length	14	-7386.68	14801.46	47.33	0.00	0.00
	smoothers by area + inflorescence length + latitude	15	-7386.26	14802.63	48.50	0.00	
	single smoother + inflorescence length + stem height + longitude	10	-7436.03	14892.11	137.98	0.00	0.00
	single smoother + inflorescence length + stem height + initial stem density + longitude	11	-7435.44	14892.94	138.81	0.00	
	single smoother + inflorescence length + stem height + latitude	10	-7436.95	14893.95	139.82	0.00	0.00
	single smoother + inflorescence length + stem height + longitude + latitude	11	-7436.02	14894.11	139.98	0.00	
	single smoother + inflorescence length + stem height + initial stem density + longitude + latitude	12	-7435.42	14894.90	140.77	0.00	
	single smoother + inflorescence length + stem height + initial stem density + latitude	11	-7436.51	14895.08	140.95	0.00	
	single smoother + inflorescence length + stem height	9	-7438.70	14895.45	141.32	0.00	0.00
	single smoother + inflorescence length + stem height + initial stem density	10	-7438.24	14896.54	142.41	0.00	
	single smoother + inflorescence length + longitude	9	-7446.08	14910.20	156.07	0.00	0.00
	single smoother + inflorescence length + latitude	9	-7446.86	14911.76	157.63	0.00	0.00
	single smoother + inflorescence length + longitude + latitude	10	-7446.08	14912.21	158.08	0.00	
	single smoother + inflorescence length	8	-7449.03	14914.10	159.97	0.00	0.00
	smoothers by area	13	-7639.81	15305.71	551.58	0.00	0.00
	single smoother	7	-7677.87	15369.77	615.64	0.00	0.00

Figure S3. The derivative curves (*i.e.*, GAMM splines) for the models evaluating how the proportion of stems that are fertile (first row), the number of inflorescences (second row), the length of the longest inflorescence (third row), and the flower density (fourth row) of the five tallest *L. salicaria* stems per quadrat changed over time. Solid black lines are model estimates and shading is the 95% credible intervals—green for when metrics of *L. salicaria* performance are predicted to increase with time (*i.e.*, $y > 0$) and orange for when metrics of *L. salicaria* performance are predicted to decrease with time (*i.e.*, $y < 0$). These estimates are significant if the 95% credible intervals do not overlap with the x-axis (*i.e.*, $y = 0$). The edf (estimated degrees freedom) represents the ‘wiggliness’ of the curve—edf values increase the more ‘turns’ in the derivative curve, while edf values approaching one represent an increasingly linear relationship between the derivative and time (* $P < 0.02$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$; splines are only considered significant if $P < 0.02$, as per Wood (2006)). The rug (*i.e.*, tick marks on the inner margin of the x-axis) represent when data was collected. How the performance of the five tallest *L. salicaria* stems in each quadrat changed over time was highly region specific. The performance of the five tallest *L. salicaria* stems per quadrat often did not change over time for our sites in Eastern Lake Ontario and in the Hudson River Valley (1st and 3rd column, respectively), but experienced periods of increasing performance over time in Montezuma (2nd column) and periods of decreasing performance over time in Western New York (4th column). The best models for metrics of five tallest performance always included separate splines for each

region. Note: we constrained the x-axis to only visualize model predictions for the range of time for which the data were collected in each specific region.

Model selection and summary of whether the five tallest *L. salicaria* stems a reliable proxy for all *L. salicaria* stems (Tables S9 & 10)

Table S9. Candidate models for evaluating whether change in mean *L. salicaria* stem height differed between measuring all *L. salicaria* stems vs. only the five tallest *L. salicaria* stems per quadrat (i.e., Box 1). As described for previous tables, k refers to the maximum allowed number of turning points in the spline, with k=1 representing a linear relationship. $\Delta AICc$ is calculated as the lowest model AICc value subtracted from the AICc of the given model. Akaike weight (w_i) is the relative likelihood that the model is explaining the data better than the remaining models in the set (i.e., the model likelihood normalized by the sum of all model likelihoods).

Model	k	-log-lik	AICc	$\Delta AICc$	w_i
method : time + method : stem density + method + time + stem density	10	-8878.10	17776.32	0.00	1.00
method : stem density + method + time + stem density	9	-8904.65	17827.40	51.08	0.00
method : time + method + time + stem density	9	-8908.30	17834.70	58.38	0.00
method + time + stem density	8	-8917.23	17850.53	74.21	0.00
method + stem density	7	-8921.41	17856.88	80.56	0.00
method + time	7	-8967.80	17949.67	173.35	0.00
method	6	-8974.79	17961.63	185.31	0.00
time + stem density	7	-8994.09	18002.25	225.93	0.00
stem density	6	-8998.22	18008.48	232.16	0.00
time	6	-9041.05	18094.15	317.83	0.00
null	5	-9047.98	18105.99	329.67	0.00

Table S10. Model output for the best model for evaluating whether change in mean *L. salicaria* stem height differed between measuring all stems vs. only the five tallest stems per quadrat.

Predictor Variables	χ^2	df	P-value
method	14.04	1.00	< 0.001
time	15.42	1.00	< 0.001
stem density	110.6	1.00	< 0.001
method x time	3.41	1.00	0.06
method x stem density	61.41	1.00	< 0.001

References:

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